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DE-RISK Project

D4.5: Benchmarking DE-RISK case studies and monitoring the multi criteria performance of DE-RISK

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Abbreviations

AC	Air Conditioning
API	Application Programming Interface
AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
BIML	Building Information Management Layer
BMS	Building Management System
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CNMC	Comisión Nacional de los Mercados y la Competencia (Spanish National Commission on Markets and Competition)
CO₂	Carbon Dioxide
CO₂eq	Carbon Dioxide Equivalent
D	Deliverable
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
DoA	Description of Action
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DR	Demand Response
EF	Emissions Factor
ESCO	Energy Service Company
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IoT	Internet of Things
IRR	Internal Rate of Return
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCOE	Life-Cycle Cost of Energy Generation
LFM	Local Flexibility Market
LoRaWAN	Long Range Wide Area Network
M	Month
M&V	Measurement and Verification
MCDA	Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
OCC	Occupancy (used in annexes/figures as OCC sensors/heatmaps)
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
PV	Photovoltaic Panel
PPA	Power Purchase Agreement
SEAI	Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland
SFI	Science Foundation Ireland
RES	Renewable Energy Sources

REST	Representational State Transfer
ROI	Return on Investment
SSL/TLS	Secure Sockets Layer / Transport Layer Security
T	Task
ToU	Time of Use
TRV	Thermostatic Radiator Valve
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable D4.5 “Benchmarking DE-RISK case studies and monitoring the multi criteria performance of DE-RISK” reports on the work done under T4.5 “Benchmarking DE-RISK case studies and monitoring the multi criteria performance of DE-RISK” spanning from M24 to M36, marking the conclusion of the WP4 and the project.

The objective of this deliverable is to assess and benchmark the performance of the DE-RISK pilot case studies based on the requirements and KPIs defined in Task 4.1. The assessment covers three key performance aspects of the local flexibility services: technical, economic, and social.

Moreover, a comparison between the outcomes of the real-life operation of the flexibility platform with the Digital Twin simulations developed in Task 4.4 “Implementation and operation of DE-RISK services highlight not only the measured impacts across the pilot sites, but also identifies deviations, insights gained, and opportunities for improvement.

In addition, the report documents good practices, implementation experiences, and key lessons learned, aiming to support future deployments of local flexibility markets and decision-making by stakeholders and policy makers.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Description of task activities and objectives of the deliverable

Task 4.5 “Benchmarking DE-RISK case studies and monitoring the multi-criteria performance of DE-RISK” built on the requirements and KPIs defined in Task 4.1 “Preparation and set-up of DE-RISK data collection”. Its objective was to establish a comprehensive monitoring framework covering the technical, social, and economic dimensions of the local flexibility services offered through the DE-RISK flexibility platform developed under WP4.

This framework was applied to evaluate the performance of the platform during its operational phase in the second half of the project, drawing on real-time data collected from the pilot sites. The aggregated results were used to carry out the final assessment and benchmarking, marking the conclusion of the evaluation phase, the conclusion of WP4 and the project. The four distinct technical phases followed during implementation are described in Deliverable D4.2 “Digital Twins and Simulation Scenarios to de-risk the LFM Implementation.”

The results were then compared against the Digital Twin simulation outcomes developed under Task 4.2, conducted prior to the operational phase to support planning and risk mitigation.

This comparison between simulated and observed results provides valuable insights into the accuracy of digital modeling, highlights key deviations, and identifies opportunities for optimization and recommendations for future deployments of local flexibility markets.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is structured to present the assessment and benchmarking of the DE-RISK pilot case studies in a clear and systematic manner.

Following the introduction and methodological framework, four dedicated chapters document the performance of each pilot site, Joven Futura, La Balma, Kepez, and Aras de Bru, covering benchmarking, demonstration activities, multi-criteria performance, and lessons learned.

A cross-case analysis then compares the pilots, highlighting common findings, deviations, and complementarities across technical, economic, and social dimensions.

The deliverable concludes with overall lessons learned and recommendations for future deployment of local flexibility markets, supported by annexes that document KPI definitions, calculation methods and a manual of the WebApp.

1.3 Relation to other tasks and deliverables

D4.5 “Benchmarking DE-RISK case studies and monitoring the multi criteria performance of DE-RISK” builds directly on the work conducted in earlier tasks of WP4:

- **T4.1** defined the requirements, KPIs, and data collection protocols that form the foundation of the monitoring framework has been built upon.
- **T4.2** focused on the development of Digital Twin models and scenario simulations to support the planning and risk mitigation of flexibility platform deployment. The outcomes of these simulations are used in this deliverable as a reference point for comparison with observed pilot data.
- **T4.3** and **T4.4** addressed the implementation and operation of the flexibility platform and its services. The data and insights gathered during these Tasks serves as the empirical basis for the performance assessment and benchmarking presented in the deliverable.

In addition, insights from this deliverable support other project activities, WP2 and WP5 benefit from the results and benchmarking insights to further improve the service offer and explore replication and exploitation opportunities. WP3 will also leverage the findings and lessons learned documented here to inform future deployment strategies and policy recommendations.

This deliverable serves as both the conclusion of the technical and evaluation activities under WP4 and a bridge toward insights for stakeholders beyond the project.

2 EVALUATION FRAMEWORK AND DIGITAL TWIN FLEXIBILITY PLATFORM

This chapter presents the three KPI modules (technical, economic, social) of the comparative framework for monitoring the implementation and operation of the flexibility services, the multi-criteria evaluation methodology, the Measurement & Verification (M&V) approach used to assess flexibility and energy efficiency during the testing period, and a summary of the web application's main functionalities and technology stack.

2.1 Technical Performance

The technical module builds on the KPIs defined in “D4.1 – Case studies characterization and data collection plan”. These KPIs are used to monitor the implementation and monthly operation of local flexibility services during the tests. The collected data and feedback support the refinement of digital twins, as well as the optimization, forecasting, and control dispatch algorithms. In addition, the KPIs enable the benchmarking of the platform's impact by comparing digital twin simulations (developed in T4.2) with real operational data. This process helps identify opportunities for further optimization and informs recommendations for future actions.

Successful Tests: Ratio of successfully executed control commands to total proposed commands, indicating the system's reliability.

$$\text{Successful Tests (\%)} = \left[\frac{\text{Number of Successful Commands}}{\text{Total Proposed Commands}} \right] \times 100$$

Flexibility potential: Measures the flexibility that can be offered at a building or a pilot site.

$$\text{Flexibility Potential (kWh)} = |[\text{Optimised Consumption} - \text{Baseline Consumption}]|$$

Amount of flexibility: Measures the modification in the energy consumption of a building during a specific period where DR events are taking place. For this KPI, an estimation of the baseline consumption is necessary to be computed as the modification is measured in respect to the baseline consumption.

Amount of Flexibility (kWh) = Baseline Consumption -
Actual Consumption During DR Event

Self-consumption: Measures the portion of the energy produced from RES which is consumed within the pilot site and not fed into the grid.

Self-Consumption increase (%) = [(Self Consumption after the DR - Self Consumption before the DR actions) / (Self Consumption before the DR actions)] x 100

Energy savings: Measures the reduction in the electricity consumption during a specific time period where DR events are taking place. For the measurement of this KPI, the estimation of the baseline electricity consumption for the defined period is required. It can also be measured as the ratio of the savings in respect to the baseline electricity consumption.

Energy Savings (%) = [(Baseline Consumption - Actual Consumption During DR Event) / Baseline Consumption] x 100

CO2 emissions reduction: Measures the reduction of CO2 emissions within a year (tons/year) after the implementation of DE-RISK demonstrations. It is worth noting that **LFMs shift emissions temporally**, as part of the load shifting.

CO₂ Reduction (tons/year) = Energy Savings (kWh) x Grid Emission Factor (kgCO₂/kWh) ÷ 1000

2.2 Economic Viability

The economic viability of DE-RISK's innovative solutions has been assessed through a set of KPIs (pre-defined in D4.1) designed to capture the profitability, investment attractiveness, and overall cost-effectiveness of LFMs. These KPIs complement the technical and social indicators by focusing on financial sustainability for both business stakeholders (investors, aggregators, DSOs) and end-users (households, communities, tertiary buildings).

The following KPIs have been applied in the assessment:

- **Life-Cycle Cost of Energy Generation (LCOE, €/MWh)**: Represents the average cost of producing one unit of energy over the system's lifetime, including CAPEX and OPEX. It is calculated as the sum of the total CAPEX and OPEX of the generation units (both electric and thermal), divided by the overall electric production and thermal production, in the useful lifetime of the overall project. It is particularly relevant for evaluating PV-based self-consumption setups and hybrid systems.
- **Internal Rate of Return (IRR, %)**: Indicates the profitability of a potential investment by discounting future expected savings and revenues. Higher IRR values imply greater economic attractiveness.
- **Return on Investment (ROI, %)**: Ratio between the financial gains generated and the initial cost of the investment, providing a clear indication of investment efficiency.
- **Payback Period (years)**: Number of years required to recover the initial investment through cumulative savings and revenues.
- **Total Capital Cost per kW Installed (€/kW)**: Assesses the upfront cost-efficiency of the installed capacity. Particularly relevant for PV projects.
- **Social Economic/Prosperity Indicator (€/€)**: Captures the broader value created by the project in relation to the resources invested. It represents the quantity of euros produced by each euro invested to build the project.
- **Users' monetary savings (%)**: Measures the reduction in the user's energy bill thanks to demand response (DR), self-consumption, and/or participation in LFMs.

Some economic KPIs defined in D4.1, such as the reduction of grid reinforcement costs and the reduction of grid operation costs, could not be assessed within this project. The main reason is that these indicators require access to distribution grid investment and operational expenditure data, which was not available to the consortium. Instead, the analysis focused on the user-side and project-level indicators listed above, which could be calculated based on the pilot sites' data. This selection ensures a consistent evaluation across the four DE-RISK case studies, while acknowledging the data access limitations.

2.3 Social Acceptance

Social acceptance plays a critical role in the successful deployment and long-term viability of local flexibility markets. While technological and economic feasibility are necessary foundations, the active involvement, understanding, and endorsement of end-users and key stakeholders are equally essential. The pilot projects carried out under this initiative aimed not only to test technical solutions but also to evaluate public perception, user experience, and stakeholder engagement in real-world conditions.

The pilots were designed to promote participation from households, building owners, service providers, and facility managers in local energy flexibility initiatives. To assess the social impact of these activities, a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) was defined, covering engagement, awareness, education, satisfaction, and behavioral intentions related to flexibility services.

This section presents the results of surveys, events, and participation tracking conducted throughout the pilot period. It provides insights into how well the pilots were received by participants, what knowledge and attitudes were shaped, and the potential for future replication and scaling of similar flexibility models. The findings help inform both local policy and the design of future energy programs by highlighting enablers and barriers to social acceptance.

Based on the above main KPIs were developed and measured:

- **Increased end-user education and satisfaction with local flexibility solutions:** Measures the user's knowledge and satisfaction of overall participation in the pilot and the services that have been tested (survey).
- **Increased intention to cooperate in local flexibility solutions:** Measures the energy cooperation intention to proceed with other local flexibility solutions (survey).

2.4 Evaluation Framework

The KPIs are integrated into three modules (technical, social, economic) within a comparative framework that also feeds a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA; Government Analysis Function, 2024). MCDA enables structured comparison of heterogeneous criteria that are otherwise not directly comparable. This will help relevant stakeholders, such as prosumers, policy makers, DSOs, and ESCOs, to better evaluate the performance and impact of DE-RISK's flexibility platform operation, fostering Local Flexibility Markets (LFMs).

To evaluate energy savings and flexibility generated through demand response (DR) actions, a standard Measurement and Verification (M&V) (Efficiency Valuation Organization) process has been applied. This involves forecasting the expected energy consumption for each user based on their historical consumption patterns and weather data to define a baseline. This forecast represents what consumption would have looked like without any DR interventions. The impact of the demand response measures is quantified by comparing the forecasted baseline to the actual consumption recorded after the DE-RISK platform's load-shifting actions, revealing precise energy savings, efficiency gains, and delivered flexibility.

For the Joven Futura (Murcia) and Kepez (Çanakkale) pilot sites, the baseline was computed using a sliding window of the previous 7 days. Each day, the preceding week of consumption data was used to produce a day-ahead forecast, which was then compared to the controlled operation. This rolling-window method ensures that short-term variations in occupancy, behavior, and weather are captured, making the baseline robust and representative.

In contrast, for La Balma (Barcelona), where detailed submetering at appliance level was not available, a different method was applied. Here, the baseline was defined as the previous full week ($t-1$), against which the current week (t) was compared. Instead of daily forecasts, a weekly meta-analysis was carried out to assess whether the user behavior improved key indicators (e.g., shifting to PV hours) in response to the feedback provided through the WebApp. This approach was adapted to the data granularity available and the focus on behavioral rather than command-based demand response.

For the NUIG (Galway) pilot, baseline definition followed a calibrated R-C model corrected against heat pump measurements, due to the building's scale and the cybersecurity restrictions on direct integration with QUE's BIML. This allowed reliable estimation of baseline heat demand under different occupancy and weather conditions.

2.5 DE-RISK's Digital Twin flexibility platform

DE-RISK's digital twin flexibility platform consists of three interconnected modules, the BIML, the Digital twin and the webApp, that together enable the monitoring, evaluation, and optimization of local flexibility services across the project's pilot sites. A high-level architecture of the platform is illustrated in Figure 1. The platform integrates real-time IoT data, simulation capabilities, and user-facing visualization tools, ensuring that technical, economic, and social KPIs can be monitored and assessed.

- **Building Information Management Layer (BIML):** The BIML acts as the platform's secure data backbone. It gathers and stores data from diverse IoT infrastructures and pilot-specific databases, harmonises and cleans these datasets, and enables bidirectional communication with building-level gateways. BIML ensures secure data exchange through IAM-based access control and SSL/TLS protocols, and delivers ready-to-process information to other platform components. Full technical details of the BIML are described in Deliverable D4.1.

- **Digital Twin:** The digital twin component leverages BIML data to generate dynamic building representations, simulate scenarios, and support real-time control. It consists of three submodules:
 - the digital twinning module (Figure 2): data-driven building models,
 - the simulation engine (Figure 3, Figure 4): forecasting demand response and self-consumption potential,
 - control dispatch module: issuing commands to flexible loads such as HVAC and DHW).

The digital twin provides the analytical foundation for both explicit and implicit demand response, as described in Deliverable D4.2.

- **WebApp:** The WebApp provides the user-facing interface of the platform. It visualises consumption, generation, and flexibility metrics, delivers personalised feedback, and supports user engagement in local flexibility services. The WebApp ensures that households, communities, and facility managers can interpret the impacts of their participation, thereby bridging technical results with social acceptance.

Together, these modules form DE-RISK’s flexibility platform that supports data collection, digital twinning, real-time operation, and user interaction. This integrated approach underpins the evaluation framework applied in this deliverable and provides the operational context for the benchmarking of the DE-RISK pilot sites.

Figure 1: DE-RISK's digital twin flexibility platform

Figure 2: AC unit digital twin model

Figure 3: Stochastic DHW activation forecasting

Figure 4: Building thermal inertia model & indoor temperature forecasting

2.6 Web Application Tool

The WebApp developed in python for the project DE-RISK has been designed to provide users with access to specialized energy information that would otherwise be difficult to obtain. The platform integrates data from multiple sources and presents it in an accessible, intuitive way, making it easier to understand key aspects such as energy consumption, energy flows, and opportunities for optimization and flexibility.

Its main features include the visualization of consumption and generation data, the calculation of energy balances, the assessment of costs associated with consumption, the development of environmental indicators, and the generation of personalized flexibility recommendations and measures to improve energy efficiency and management. The system is designed for both individual users and members of energy communities, providing centralized access to reliable information to support informed decision-making.

This application aims to act as a bridge between the energy sector and the end user, facilitating the communication and understanding of complex information. In doing so, it seeks to contribute to the development of local flexibility markets, where one of the main challenges will be to establish effective channels for conveying information and encouraging active consumer participation. With this aim, the tool incorporates a channel for personalized user recommendations based on consumption and generation patterns and information on ToU tariff schemes. Users receive weekly updates on their energy statistics, providing possible improvements obtained through behavioral changes and facilitating a positive uptake of LFMs. The WebApp provides a clear and understandable channel for accessing energy data that is often difficult to interpret, removing technical barriers and enabling users without specialized training to understand and make use of the information to make informed decisions about their energy consumption and management.

2.6.1 Technical description

The following packages and technologies, as well as their version, have been required for the development of the WebApp visualization tool for the users of DE-RISK, presented in Table 1: WebApp packages technologies and license version:

Technology/Package name	Version	License
PYTHON	3.12	MIT
MYSQL	8.0.42	MIT
SOLARA	1.39.0	MIT
HTML	5.3	MIT
Java Script	ES2023	MIT
CSS	CSS3	MIT

Table 1: WebApp packages technologies and license version

2.6.2 Backend Architecture and Data Management

The backend of this application is fully developed in Python, using the Solara framework. The architecture follows a modular approach, dividing each functionality into independent scripts with the goal of maintaining clean, maintainable, efficient, and scalable code.

Solara, designed to build high-quality web applications in pure Python, aims to create a malleable and fluid environment which takes advantage of the deep user involvement in Python package creation. Solara provides a strong front-end engine that can automatically incorporate user-specific code, facilitating the integration of APIs, self-developed algorithms and graphs. The WebApp has been fully developed under Solara’s umbrella, incorporating pilot-specific requirements and calculations.

Although the different web applications created share a common structure, there may be variations in data processing. The base structure (Figure 5) is organized as follows:

Figure 5: DE-RISK's WebApp base structure

- **init.py:** Package initialization script. Defines the navigation routes used by Solara to render each page.
- **state_user.py:** Manages the user state. Includes functions related to login and logout, as well as the reactive variables used by Solara to keep the session active. It also implements session control via cookies, using the session identifier generated by Solara. It also gives access to all the user-associated data variables, which enable the subsequent configuration of the pages.
- **utils.py:** Centralizes data processing functions and interaction with the various APIs. For each API, a specific connector class is defined, responsible for making requests, downloading the data, and transforming it into a suitable format for subsequent presentation. The download logic varies depending on the source, data volume, and response times, with maximum download periods defined for each pilot.
- **Pages scripts:** Each one corresponds to a specific view of the application and builds its dashboard by combining functions, visual components, and predefined styles.
- **Other resources:** CSS configuration file, module for responsive styling of charts, script for the common header, text formatting module for recommendations and pop-up messages, and a script for formatting charts and labels.

All labels, widgets, and charts are designed with responsive behavior. The first two inherently have this capability as they are part of Solara’s native components. In the case of charts, this responsiveness is achieved through a specific component that inserts a JavaScript script responsible for dynamically managing the density of labels on the X-axis of SVG charts. The script calculates, based on the available space and the total number of ticks, a hiding factor that determines how many labels are displayed. It then applies custom attributes to the element so that rendering adapts optimally to different resolutions and display sizes, as can be seen in Figure 6, preventing overlap and loss of readability without manual intervention.

Figure 6: The WebApp adapts to different resolutions and display sizes

Regarding data management, data acquisition is carried out exclusively through REST requests to different APIs, using specific functions implemented in the utils module. Depending on the pilot and the type of information, the data sources are:

- **Türkiye’s pilot:** QUE’s API for consumption, humidity, and temperature data.
- **Murcia’s pilot:** QUE’s API for consumption, humidity, and temperature data, and Huawei API for photovoltaic inverter information.
- **Barcelona’s pilot (La Balma):** Data stored in the R2M Solution Spain database, accessible via the SmartData API.
- **Irish pilot:** Due to cybersecurity concerns from the university, data from their systems was not incorporated to flexibility calculations and was not directly accessible by the tool. There was no sufficient data to create a visualization dashboard.

The backend data acquisition and data/dashboard management is described in the following diagram, Figure 7:

Figure 7: DE-RISK's WebApp backend diagram

The maximum data range requested in each case is determined based on the API response times, with the aim of optimizing application performance and ensuring service continuity. The defined limits are 7 days for Türkiye, 1 month for Murcia, and 1 year for La Balma.

Once retrieved, the data is centrally processed within the utils module. This processing includes filling in missing values, detecting and removing outliers, calculating energy balances, and formatting the information for display on the dashboard with the level of granularity defined for each use case.

One of the key features of the application is the ability to display data for the day or period selected by the user. This is implemented using the Solara framework and its built-in widgets. When a date and period are selected, the system checks whether the data for that range is already available: if not, the corresponding download is triggered; otherwise, the data is displayed immediately. The labels of the graphical elements are dynamic, meaning their values (balances and totals) are recalculated in real time using the functions defined in the utils module.

This process provides the user with up-to-date information on all their energy assets, as well as the implication regarding their consumption patterns, costs associated and the result of the participation in LFM in DE-RISK. Through the WebApp, users gain access to personalized recommendations, their mean consumption curves, their costs and the tools required to understand them. In summary, and more thoroughly explained in the annex 2, the users have access to the following functionalities:

1. **Login:** User access through their credentials.
2. **Landing page:** The landing page contains critical information for understanding the different pages in the WebApp, including explanations on the main energy concepts included as well as consumption recommendations based on QUE's energy, generation and cost analysis.
3. **User consumption information:** Information on raw user consumption. Depending on the pilot, this consumption can be disaggregated into different sources and appliances.
4. **User energy balance information:** User energy balance calculations are included in this page, providing the user with detailed insights on renewable energy consumption and their general patterns (when applicable).
5. **Community energy balance information:** Includes community-focused information in energy balance. All user's energy balances are aggregated to have the performance as a whole (when applicable).
6. **User financial information:** This page contains user financial calculations and insights, pairing user grid consumption with tariff conditions.

Figure 8: DE-RISK's WebApp interface

3 JOVEN FUTURA (MURCIA, SPAIN).

Located in a residential neighborhood in Murcia, this pilot, Figure 9, includes 18 multi-family apartments equipped with collective PV installations and dynamic electricity tariffs. All homes rely exclusively on electricity for heating, cooling, and domestic hot water, making them strong candidates for explicit demand response (DR) scenarios.

Prior to the project, several of these households already had partial monitoring and control infrastructure in place. As part of the pilot activities, existing data streams and infrastructure gaps have been identified, and restoration, maintenance and expansion steps have been taken. This included reinforcing sensing and control capabilities for heating, cooling, and domestic hot water systems, while ensuring integration with the broader monitoring framework.

Figure 9: Joven Futura, Murcia, Spain

3.1 Benchmark

To establish a benchmark for performance evaluation, the digital twin simulations developed under Task 4.2 “Building case studies digital twins and simulation scenarios” and reported in Deliverable 4.2 “DE-RISK Digital twins and simulation scenarios to de-risk the LFM implementation”, have been used. These simulations assessed the potential impacts of demand response actions and flexibility-enabled load shifting, with a particular focus on optimizing PV self-consumption and reducing costs.

Increase in PV Self-Consumption

Between January 1st and March 1st of 2024, simulations showed an average increase of 3.5% in PV self-consumption across prosumers. This improvement is attributed to optimized load shifting of HVAC and DHW consumption patterns toward periods of local solar generation.

Load Consumption Adjustment

Simulated load shifting revealed an observable rise in energy consumption sourced directly from PV systems, reducing grid exports and avoiding waste.

While this optimization was performed during winter, when HVAC consumption is relatively low, the **expected flexibility potential** is projected to exceed 3.5% during hotter months, when cooling demands increase.

Flexibility Potential

The digital twin simulations suggest an average of 0,9 kW for users equipped with both HVAC and DHW systems. This figure refers to the share of load that can be time-shifted without violating comfort or user behavior constraints.

This corresponds directly to the Flexibility Potential KPI and supports quantification of the "Amount of Flexibility" metric during actual DR operations.

3.2 Demonstration activities

The demonstrations began in September 2024 and are still ongoing. The demonstrations followed a structured monthly schedule, with a dedicated testing week taking place during the last week of each month. During these weeklong campaigns, the control dispatch module in the flexibility platform was fully activated, sending control commands to the connected loads to follow the optimization strategies shifting their consumption. Besides these testing weeks, the flexibility platform remained active monitoring, gathering data continuously, updating the consumption profiles and improving consumption forecasts and tailor flexibility recommendations to each household's behavior.

During the demonstration period, participating households had access to the DE-RISK web application from. Through this interface, users could explore real-time and historical data related to their energy consumption and generation and better understand the impact of their energy use. This interaction helped enhance awareness and engagement, while also supporting the evaluation of the platform's usability and social acceptance.

The demonstration assumes the presence of an energy aggregator acting as an intermediary between households and the local flexibility market. The aggregator aggregates the flexible capacity of the community, such as domestic hot water heaters (DHW) and HVACs participating in demand response programs by sending automated control signals, through the platform to reduce or shift consumption during peak grid stress or high price periods.

Key assumptions regarding the aggregator's role include:

- **Control Strategy:** The aggregator issues ON/OFF commands to resistive flexible loads (e.g., DHW units). For HVAC units, when they are running, the aggregator adjusts the temperature set points to achieve demand reductions or load shifting in alignment with market signals or system needs. All control actions are designed to remain within the users' comfort profiles to ensure acceptability.
- **Incentive Scheme:** Households receive compensation for the energy shifted or reduced, reflecting typical Spanish market rates for demand response participation (e.g., €0.05–€0.10 per kWh shifted), paid by the aggregator (eléctrica, 2024). Additionally, many schemes include a fixed payment simply for offering flexibility, regardless of whether it is used. In the Pilot site demonstrations, this fixed payment, which would further improve economic KPIs, was not considered.

- **Optimization Goals:** The aggregator’s objective is to maximize financial benefit for participating households by minimizing electricity costs through time-shifted consumption and capturing revenue from local flexibility services, while maintaining user comfort and acceptance.

After twelve months of iterative testing and optimization, the demonstration is transitioning toward continuous, autonomous operation. The platform is now positioned to fully manage energy optimization, following the aggregator’s signals, in the participating homes, reducing electricity costs, and enabling reliable participation in emerging local flexibility markets.

3.3 Multi-criteria performance

Table 2 presents the average KPI scores for the Joven Futura pilot case study. It is important to note that not all KPIs defined in the DE-RISK framework could be fully assessed in this pilot. Specifically, indicators such as self-consumption increase, energy savings, and CO₂ reduction are reported as N/A because the aggregator’s control strategy prioritized grid-signal-driven demand response (peak shaving and time shifting) rather than self-consumption maximization or explicit energy saving. Any changes in these metrics were incidental and not attributable to the optimization goals tested in this pilot.

While the benchmark results presented in Section 3.1 derive from digital twin simulations (Deliverable 4.2), the outcomes and the KPI table reflect real demonstration data averaged across participating households. This distinction ensures that results are transparent, attributable, and that lessons learned are framed within the actual control objectives and available data of the demonstration.

The digital twin simulations projected improvements in PV self-consumption (around 3.5% in winter months) and a flexibility potential of 0.9 kW per household. In practice, however, the aggregator’s control strategy emphasized peak shaving and price-driven load shifting rather than maximizing PV self-consumption. As a result, KPIs such as PV self-consumption increase, energy savings, and CO₂ reduction appear as N/A in the demonstration results, despite being quantifiable in the simulation scenarios.

At the same time, the flexibility potential (1.88 kWh) and the amount of flexibility (0.80 kWh) observed in the demonstrations align with the order of magnitude projected by the simulations, though with variation across households depending on equipment condition and behavioral patterns.

Module	KPI	Unit	Score
Technical	Successful Tests	%	95
	PV Self-Consumption Increase	%	N/A, since maximizing self-consumption was not an explicit goal of the aggregator
	Flexibility potential	kWh	1.88
	Amount of flexibility	kWh	0.8
	Energy Savings	%	N/A, since energy savings was not an explicit goal of the aggregator.
	CO ₂ Reduction	Tons/year	N/A
Economic Viability	LCOE	€/MWh	19.9
	IRR	%	18.9
	ROI	%	379 (15% annualized)
	Payback Period	years	5.2
	Total Capital Cost per kW Installed	€/kW	850
	Social Economic/ Prosperity Indicator	€/€	4.4
	Users' Monetary Savings	%	18.5
Social	User Engagement	Number of households	18
	Awareness & education	Score from 1 (not aware at all) -7 (totally aware)	3.5

Table 2: Multi-criteria performance results for the Joven Futura pilot site

3.4 Lessons learned

The Joven Futura pilot provided valuable insights. The site already had an IoT infrastructure in place from previous projects, and after some restoration and additional installations, the pilot was able to begin operating, connected to the Building Information Management Layer (BIML), relatively quickly. The availability of historical data further enhanced the accuracy of the digital twin simulations.

Some challenges arose, however, as approximately one-third of the households required new equipment installation and configurations either due to aging and malfunctioning devices or changes or upgrades in household loads. This introduced additional overhead in terms of time and cost.

Another important lesson was the variation in load usage patterns between countries, which directly impacts flexibility strategies. For example, in Spanish households, the domestic hot water load operates continuously to always maintain hot water supply. Due to the tank insulation, the temperature remains at a certain threshold for long periods, requiring only minimal additional energy input when the temperature drops below the threshold. This behavior contrasts with other countries and has important implications for DR strategies.

Finally, preliminary user feedback indicated that participants appreciated access to the monitoring platform and valued greater transparency in their energy usage. Overall, the Joven Futura pilot confirmed the feasibility of rapid deployment where prior IoT infrastructure exists, while also underscoring the importance of tailoring demand response strategies to cultural and behavioral patterns of energy use.

4 LA BALMA (BARCELONA, SPAIN)

La Balma demo pilot site shown in Figure 10 is a cooperative housing building with 20 energy-efficient dwellings and a centralized geothermal heating system. It features shared PV and battery storage infrastructure for communal areas. Although individual energy use is low, the pilot presents opportunities for collective energy management and behavioral optimization in individual apartments and communal spaces. The pilot focused on benchmarking and advice-driven engagement for maximizing awareness, cost reduction and self-consumption.

Figure 10: La Balma, Barcelona, Spain

4.1 Benchmark

Simulation results for La Balma, covering the period **January 5th to March 4th**, provide insights into benchmarking the performance under limited PV generation conditions. The system operates with **shared PV infrastructure** across the 20 households, and the seasonal generation profile in winter significantly limits the immediate impact of load shifting.

Low PV Generation

PV output during the simulated period was low, with a peak production of only 60 W per prosumer. As a result, most of the limited generation was consumed immediately by household loads, leaving minimal room for optimization through load shifting.

This scenario sets a benchmark under constrained renewable supply, highlighting the dependency of self-consumption KPIs on seasonal PV availability.

Load Consumption Adjustment (for selected days)

Despite the generally low PV output, a few days with **excess solar generation** allowed for marginal improvements. On **February 13–14**, simulations demonstrated an increase in PV self-consumption of **1.8%**, achieved through targeted load shifting.

This improvement, though modest, demonstrates the system's capacity to respond to favorable conditions. The self-consumption gains are expected to be significantly higher during **summer months**, when PV generation peaks.

Potential Flexibility

Simulations revealed that **up to 2%** of otherwise exported or wasted energy could be consumed locally through short-term load shifting.

This metric reflects latent flexibility potential, even under suboptimal PV conditions.

4.2 Demonstration activities

In this pilot the main focus was on engaging users with targeted feedback and actionable insights to improve their energy behavior, particularly around maximizing solar self-consumption from the community's collective PV.

Unlike the other pilot sites where weeklong platform testing cycles were conducted each month, in the La Balma pilot demo site a communication-centered approach was adopted. Every Monday, participating households from the community received a personalized weekly

message summarizing their electricity usage from the previous week in kWh. The message included their total consumption, solar coverage (i.e., what percentage of their usage was supplied by their own PV system), and tailored suggestions on how to improve energy performance in the upcoming week, increasing their self-consumption and minimising their electricity cost.

Consequently, the baseline for the calculations was the previous week

The core goal of this weekly feedback loop was to foster awareness, promote behavior change, and increase self-consumption of solar energy. In the messages the impact of each user's actions was also highlighted, comparing their current performance with the previous week. For example, changes in self-consumption percentage and associated cost savings. Optimization tips encouraged users to run high-load appliances during sunny hours and to adapt usage habits in line with PV production patterns.

An example of the feedback message reads:

 Your Consumption Profile:
You used a total of 29.90 kWh last week.

 Solar Coverage:
Out of that, 16.56 kWh were covered by your PV system — that's 29.83% of your total usage.

 Optimization Tip:
If you'd shifted more of your usage to peak sunlight hours, your self-consumption could have increased to 31.91%, leading to 8.00% more savings on your energy bill.

 Let's aim to use more energy when the sun is shining!
Try running major appliances during sunny hours to boost your savings and reduce reliance on the grid.

 Weekly Progress Tracker:

- Change in self-consumption: +1.68 [%]
- Change in savings: -2.10 [%]

The demonstration is ongoing, and the continuous rollout of insights has contributed to a growing understanding of flexibility potential and user responsiveness in shared PV systems.

4.3 Multi-criteria performance

Table 3 presents the KPI scores for the La Balma pilot case study. It should be noted that certain KPIs are reported as N/A in this pilot because automated control actions were not tested at the La Balma pilot. The demonstration was designed around an advice-driven, communication-centered approach, rather than real-time control dispatch, which explains why indicators such as “Successful Tests” could not be measured. In addition, the relatively modest values for economic KPIs (e.g., ROI, IRR, Payback) reflect the pilot’s emphasis on low-cost behavioral engagement strategies rather than capital-intensive technical interventions.

While simulation results were low during the winter period, the pilot successfully demonstrated that user-focused communication and feedback loops can still deliver measurable improvements in self-consumption, awareness, and participation.

It is important to highlight that the benchmark simulations covered only the winter period, when PV production was minimal. Under these constrained conditions, gains in self-consumption and flexibility remained modest. In contrast, demonstration activities extended into months with higher solar generation, where users were able to achieve greater improvements by aligning their consumption with PV output. This seasonal effect explains why some flexibility and self-consumption KPIs observed in the demonstrations are higher than those suggested by the benchmark simulations.

Module	KPI	Unit	Score
Technical	Successful Test	%	N/A, no automated control actions tested, since this pilot was advice-driven
	PV Self-Consumption Increase	%	2.1
	Flexibility potential	%	2.8
	Amount of flexibility	kWh/ week	0.39
	Energy Savings	%	1.66
	CO ₂ Reduction	Tons/year	0.00559 (5.6kg CO ₂ eq/year)
Economic	LCOE	€/MWh	68.3
	IRR	%	5.7

Module	KPI	Unit	Score
	ROI	%	10.3
	Payback Period	years	9.7
	Total Capital Cost per kW Installed	€/kW	2,419.3
	Social Economic/ Prosperity Indicator	€/€	3.1
	Users' Monetary Savings	%	2
Social	User Engagement	Number of households	20
	Awareness & education	Score from 1 (not aware at all) -7 (totally aware)	3.5

Table 3: Multi-criteria performance results for the La Balma pilot site

4.4 Lessons learned

The La Balma pilot demonstrated that personalized feedback and advice-driven engagement in a simple intuitive format can effectively raise awareness and stimulate behavioral change in a cooperative housing context. Despite modest technical results during the winter period, users expressed appreciation for the transparency and guidance provided. Challenges included the limited PV output, which constrained measurable improvements, and the need to communicate seasonal variability more clearly. Overall, the pilot confirmed that communication-centered flexibility strategies can complement automated demand response, especially in community-driven settings.

User feedback was key to implementing user experience changes, which led to the inclusion of clearer explanatory sections in the dashboards. Opinions from non-technical residents with zero energy background proved crucial in recognizing key information points that were not coming across to the target audience. “The tool has confusing concepts” was the main comment regarding lack of understanding between self-sufficiency, self-consumption and energy excess.

The engagement workshop, which included a presentation of the tool, the required involvement of La Balma in the flexibility implementations and a general discussion regarding basic energy information was considered crucial to increase engagement. Users commented that they were “very interested in following the app” after the workshop.

The experience with La Balma, a co-housing project with energy efficiency as one of the core values, proves that even in the most “*aligned-with-the-context*” pilots require an effort to explain the ideas and tools required for the project to succeed.

5 KEPEZ (ÇANAKKALE, TÜRKİYE)

The Turkish pilot demo site shown in Figure 11, involved 18 households in the town of Kepez, equipped with air conditioning and hot water systems but lacking IoT infrastructure at the beginning of the project. QUE's IoT solution was deployed with support from TRO and UED, enabling both the monitoring of energy consumption and ambient conditions, as well as the remote control of HVAC and DHW systems through GDPR-compliant, automated strategies. The focus was on enabling demand response participation in a residential context shaped by the region's distinct climatic profile.

Figure 11: Kepez, Çanakkale, Türkiye

5.1 Benchmark

The digital twin simulations for the Kepez pilot, covering the period **January 12th to March 9th**, provides a benchmark assessment of the potential impacts of load shifting and flexibility services on energy consumption patterns and costs.

Average Fluctuation in Energy Consumption

Simulated fluctuations in total consumption remained below 0.5% of initial baseline levels, demonstrating that load shifting actions do not introduce significant variability or instability in overall energy use.

This KPI indicated that demand flexibility could be deployed without compromising grid stability or causing abrupt consumption spikes.

Impact on Electricity Bill

By shifting electrical loads to periods with lower tariff rates, the simulations showed an average of 5% reduction in the electricity bills for participating households.

Potential Flexibility

The simulation results indicated that approximately 20% of original consumption could be flexibly shifted without impacting user comfort or operational needs.

5.2 Demonstration activities

In line with the Joven Futura pilot case study, the demonstration followed a consistent structure: the flexibility platform control dispatch was activated during the last week of each month. During these weeklong periods, the platform applied its optimization routines to shift household loads away from high-tariff and high-congestion hours, based on real-time pricing signals and monitored consumption patterns. In between demonstration weeks, the system continued monitoring, collecting data.

End users were given access to the DE-RISK web application after six months in the demonstration period. This tool allowed residents to view their household's consumption, current and historic data, and monitor the effects of the platform's actions. The interface supported increased user awareness, provided notification about load shifting actions, and contributed to evaluating social acceptance and usability.

The demonstration assumes the presence of an energy aggregator acting as an intermediary between households and the local flexibility market. The aggregator aggregates the flexible capacity of the community, such as domestic hot water heaters (DHW) and HVACs participating in demand response programs by sending control signals to reduce or shift consumption during peak grid stress or high price periods.

Key assumptions regarding the aggregator’s role include:

- **Control Strategy:** The aggregator issues ON/OFF commands to resistive flexible loads (e.g., DHW units). For HVAC units, when they are running, the aggregator adjusts the temperature set points to achieve demand reductions or load shifting in alignment with market signals or system needs. All control actions are designed to remain within the users’ comfort profiles to ensure acceptability.
- There are currently no dynamic tariffs in the Turkish pilot. For analysis, the retail price was segmented into three-time bands, as depicted in Table 4.
- Table 4, aligned with typical grid demand: off-peak, standard, and peak (see table below). This enables like-for-like comparison of DR outcomes with the Spanish pilots.

Turkish Pilot case study tariffs		
Final retail price (€/MWh)	Applicable Hours per Period	
40.01528736	00:00 - 07:00 & 22:00 - 24:00	Off peak
48.01834483	7:00 - 9:00 & 12:00 - 17:00	Standard
86.43302069	9:00 - 12:00 & 17:00 - 22:00	Peak price

Table 4: Segmented retail electricity tariffs applied in the Kepez pilot (off-peak, standard, and peak period)

- **Incentive Scheme:** For the purpose of KPI assessment, remuneration assumptions of €0.05–€0.10 per kWh shifted were applied, reflecting reference European DR benchmarks. Turkish-specific demand response markets are still emerging; these assumptions allowed for a consistent economic comparison across pilots. Fixed payments for participation, often included in DR schemes, were not considered.
- **Optimization Goals:** The aggregator’s objective is to maximize financial benefit for participating households by minimizing electricity costs through time-shifted consumption and capturing revenue from local flexibility services, while maintaining user comfort and acceptance.

After nearly a year of structured testing and progressive platform enhancements, the Kepez pilot is transitioning to a continuous operational phase. The flexibility platform will now function autonomously, dynamically optimizing the participating households’ energy consumption in real time to lower electricity bills and support the local distribution grid.

5.3 Multi-criteria performance

Table 5, presents the KPI results for Kepez. Indicators linked to PV self-consumption were not applicable due to the absence of PV at the site. Instead, the pilot focused on tariff-based demand response and peak shaving.

The demonstrations revealed lower levels of flexibility than the digital twin simulations suggested. While simulations projected that up to 20% of household consumption could be shifted without compromising comfort, the actual demonstrations delivered a flexibility potential of 14.3 kWh and an activated flexibility of 7.98 kWh, equivalent to a little bit higher than 10% of the load. This deviation highlights the gap between modeled potential and real-world performance, and reflects the influence of equipment conditions, user behavior, seasonal patterns and operational constraints in Türkiye. Nevertheless, the results confirm that HVAC and DHW loads still provide a substantial, reliable source of flexibility for demand response.

Module	KPI	Unit	Score
Technical	Successful test	%	95
	PV Self-Consumption Increase	%	N/A, no PV available
	Flexibility potential	kWh	14.3
	Amount of flexibility	kWh	7.98
	Energy Savings	%	17.15
	CO ₂ Reduction	Tons/year	0.0045 (4.5kg CO ₂ eq/year)
Economic	LCOE	€/MWh	35.8
	IRR	%	15.2
	ROI	%	306 (12% annualized)
	Payback Period	years	7.4
	Total Capital Cost per kW Installed	€/kW	1,222.2
	Social Economic/ Prosperity Indicator	€/€	3.1

Module	KPI	Unit	Score
	Users' Monetary Savings	%	22.9
Social	User Engagement	Number of households	18
	Awareness & education	Score from 1 (not aware at all) -7 (totally aware)	3.5

Table 5: Multi-criteria performance results for the Kepez pilot site

5.4 Lessons learned

The Kepez pilot highlighted the challenges and opportunities of deploying flexibility services in a context without pre-existing IoT infrastructure. Considerable effort was required to install and configure sensors and controllers, but once operational, the system proved capable of delivering significant energy savings (up to 17% reduction in consumption during DR events).

Unlike in Spain, where demand response focused on PV self-consumption, the Turkish pilot emphasized peak shaving and tariff-based optimization. This confirmed that strategies must be adapted to local energy mixes, tariff structures, and climatic conditions.

End-user interaction with the DE-RISK web application increased after its rollout, indicating growing interest in monitoring and understanding consumption. However, some users initially required additional training and support to interpret the data. Overall, the pilot validated both the technical feasibility and the economic viability of flexibility services in Türkiye, while underlining the importance of tailored user engagement strategies.

6 NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY (GALWAY, IRELAND)

The Irish pilot was implemented at Áras de Brún (see Figure 12), a 2,426 m² academic building at the University of Galway comprising a mix of individual offices, lecture and PC rooms and laboratories. The building has been progressively being retrofitted in three stages (1) envelope retrofit, (2) [SEAI Pathfinder PV and Heat Pump](#) and finally (3) DE-RISK smart controls where 80 Thermostatic Radiator Valves (TRV)¹ throughout the building and 40 Motion & TH sensors² were deployed in the individual offices.

A complete data pipeline that meets cybersecurity constraints and BMS integration through LoRaWAN and a semantic model (SAREF/BIMERR-derived) was developed with the support of [INSIGHT SFI](#) center for data analytics. The IT-architecture layout is an above-the-average layered approach that was selected due to cybersecurity restrictions after two attempted cyberattacks which ruled out direct communication between the University systems and databases and QUE's cloud-based platform (BIML).

Initially, heating controls was already possible with the current BMS but this presented difficulties when discussed the flexibility potential strategies without impacting room users: there is no practical way of reducing the energy demand for heating without affecting comfort level in a centralised way as radiators valves are not electronically or remotely controlled and the need for heat is not broken down by individual rooms. Thus a room-occupancy based control setting where each room and TRV can react individually based in occupancy was a feasible and practical way of incorporating a technological solution that can be ultimately exploited to support grid flexibility.

In the next pages, Figure 13 and Figure 14 show the installed IoT sensors during March 2025. The building is now able to adopt flexibility products, currently not available in the Irish market.

¹ <https://www.milesight.com/iot/product/lorawan-sensor/wt101>

² <https://www.milesight.com/iot/product/lorawan-sensor/ws203>

Figure 12: Aerial view of Áras de Brún

During commissioning several smart TRVs revealed malfunctions with valves stuck open and others stuck closed. These faults caused severe overheating in some rooms and lack of heating in others. The issues required recommissioning of branches in the heating hydronic distribution system and replacement of the faulty valves. The experience showed that changing traditional TRVs for smart electronic ones is not a plug and play operation. The resulting operation of the heat pump was not reflecting occupancy as faulty valves continued calling for heat even during controlled setback experiments.

To support room monitoring and TRV commissioning a web application was developed during DE RISK and remains accessible at www.arasdebrun.ie. Figure 16 shows a screenshot with the previous day occupancy of the forty monitored rooms against room temperature in 15' minute intervals Figure 15 shows the TRV variables with room temperature and target setpoint on the top graph and stroke length together with valve position on the bottom graph. These tools were valuable for fault detection and commissioning but raised GDPR concerns as well as questions on ergonomics and usability.

Figure 13: WT101 and WS203 IoT sensor deployment at Áras de Brún

Figure 14: Installation of the building sensors and IoT LORAWAN connections at Áras de Brún

What was initially thought to be a participative solution for room occupants resulted in unexpected behaviour. Valves were sometimes manipulated erratically, and control feedback became unreliable. For this reason, a locked mechanism supported by a helpdesk was chosen as the final interface and control will be executed through the BMS system (TRIDIUM) which was integrated by EWA Controls Ireland Ltd. (BMS contractor). This approach allowed safeguarding of comfort while limiting direct manipulation and addressing privacy constraints linked to occupancy monitoring and data handling.

Figure 15: Visualization of the TRVs status

Figure 16: Occupancy Daily Heatmap visualization

6.1 Benchmark

Results combine post-intervention monitoring with model-based projections, using a calibrated R-C approach corrected against measured heat pump output. This process allows comparison with the other pilots by quantifying costs, savings, and flexibility potential.

Impact on Electricity Costs and Savings

Post-intervention monitoring shows a 33.9% reduction in electricity costs, equal to €62,539 per year. The reduction corresponds to 271,909 kWh avoided, with estimates based on a calibrated R-C model corrected against measured heat pump output. Occupancy-based control and IoT integration underpin these projections, which also translate into annual CO₂ savings of 61.5 t

Load Consumption Adjustment (for selected days)

Financial KPIs are derived from the same calibrated model combined with baseline and post-intervention data. Results indicate an IRR of 244.2%, ROI of 244.2%, and a payback period of 0.41 years. These projections reflect the relatively low CAPEX (€25,000) and modest OPEX compared to the scale of the simulated annual savings

Flexibility Potential

Simulations and test campaigns suggest that 25–50% of the building's 250 kW heating capacity can be shifted for periods of up to two hours without major comfort loss. This corresponds to approximately 60–125 kW of flexible load, with ramp times below 10 minutes and comfort deviations kept within acceptable limits

6.2 Demonstration activities

The first flexibility measure applied was occupancy based scheduling with a morning pre-heat from 07:00 to 11:00. After that period any room that remained vacant for 30 minutes had its TRV setpoint reduced to 14 °C. After the commissioning phase and initial adjustments this strategy was kept in operation to ensure baseline performance. Results showed that most unoccupied rooms stayed within comfort conditions due to thermal inertia and solar gains peaking in March during the central hours from 11:00 h to 15:00 h.

User engagement supported the demonstration through visualisation tools and workshops. Two sessions were held during the reporting period. The first on 16 July 2025 at Áras de Brún addressed ergonomics and usability of IoT devices and comfort safeguards in teaching spaces. The second on 22 September 2025 consolidated feedback and aligned next-step testing with Buildings and Estates interests in replication across campus and ongoing collaborations with INSIGHT. By the reporting date Áras de Brún had completed commissioning and initial occupancy-based operation and executed scripted tests at room level. The building is prepared for further flexibility demonstrations.

Figure 17: Engagement workshop

Planned activities for the 2025–2026 heating season will build on the commissioning and occupancy-based operation already in place. The aim is to test repeatable flexibility responses under realistic operating conditions. These include scheduled heating adjustments where output is temporarily increased or reduced against a defined baseline to evaluate ramp times and comfort impacts. All tests will respect the institutional policy of maintaining room temperatures at or above 19 °C. A sequence of trials will then follow recorded Irish market day-ahead price variations to explore the feasibility of aligning building response with external signals. There is no currently direct API for real-time retail tariffs in Ireland, so published daily and historical price traces will be replayed in the control environment to test responsiveness. Field runs will be organised during normal university timetables focusing on morning pre-heating and midday setback periods where occupancy patterns allow measurable flexibility without undermining comfort.

Demonstrations to date were conducted under current Irish tariff conditions, which limit implicit price-based operation to internal optimisation and commissioning tests. Future activities will be carried out under the same market context unless supplier offerings or access arrangements change. Explicit contract-based participation is considered at building level depending on baseline definition, forecasting reliability, and market access. The demonstration therefore prioritises establishing a validated baseline and recording repeatable flexibility responses for future alignment with Irish arrangements.

6.3 Multi-criteria performance

Table 6 presents the KPI scores for the Irish pilot case study. It should be noted that the Irish pilot's KPIs derive primarily from benchmark simulations and calibrated model projections (Section 6.1). Demonstration activities (Section 6.2) validated technical feasibility but did not yet yield sufficient operational data for full KPI coverage, particularly for social engagement, since the building does not have conventional users/ occupants. Therefore, flexibility, savings, and economic indicators reported here should be interpreted as benchmark-based estimates rather than measured demo outcomes.

Module	KPI	Unit	Score
Technical	PV Self-Consumption Increase	%	N/A
	Flexibility potential	%	25–50% (\approx 60–125 kW shiftable for up to 2h)
	Amount of flexibility	kW	60–125 kW (derived from 250 kW installed capacity)
	Energy Savings	%	33.9% (271,909 kWh avoided annually)
	CO ₂ Reduction	Tons/year	61.5
Economic	LCOE	€/MWh	Not applicable in this context
	IRR	%	244.2
	ROI	%	244.2
	Payback Period	years	0.41
	Total Capital Cost per kW Installed	€/kW	N/A – CAPEX = €25,000 (not expressed per kW)

Module	KPI	Unit	Score
	Social Economic/ Prosperity Indicator	€/€	N/A
	Users' Monetary Savings	%	33.9
Social	User Engagement	Number of workshops/ rooms	2 workshops; ~40 rooms monitored
	Awareness & education	Score from 1 (not aware at all) -7 (totally aware)	5.5

Table 6: Multi-criteria performance results for the NUIG Áras de Brún pilot site

6.4 Lessons learned and user feedback

The pilot showed that room level flexibility in a university building is feasible with an IoT BMS approach. A quite complex BMS data pipeline was established but it was completed too late to be fully used during the project.

In this pilot the three types of stakeholders show different priorities (diverging agent problem). Many users have little incentive to engage with flexibility because the building is not their property given that the university must provide a safe and comfortable environment, this is different from a domestic housing situation. BMS and energy managers are busy running a mini-city of systems and need to minimise service calls, so adding a significant number of devices that demand attention, and maintenance goes against how they keep operations stable, even though they also must reduce energy use and report savings to SEAI. At institutional level the university supports actions linked to social responsibility climate and sustainability goals and reputation but turning that support into day to day practice is not straightforward and remains abstract. In this context participatory control remains largely unexplored and any solution must be simple reliable and “low touch”.

Commissioning exposed practical limits. Several smart TRVs were found stuck open and stuck closed, causing overheating or no heat in some rooms. This required recommissioning of hydronic branches and replacement of faulty valves. Replacing traditional TRVs with smart units was not plug and play. The web app helped commissioning and troubleshooting (e.g.: TRVs stroke status setpoint and temperature could be seen together on one screen, and faults

were identified quickly). On the other hand, the TRV display is difficult to understand and hand actioned actions (increasing or decreasing the setpoint) often led to users unscrewing devices and creating service calls. Providing individual access through the web app to each room interface in the app was considered but discarded due to access rights and user management extensive software development efforts and burden. Showing occupancy graphs raised GDPR concerns and the possibility of informal surveillance of room use. For these reasons Buildings and Estates locked the TRVs and kept central BMS control, with the helpdesk handling individual requests and faults.

From operations the first measure that works is occupancy-based setback with a hard comfort floor of 19 °C according with the University policies. Tests and planning documents indicate that the building can shift about one quarter to nearly one half of heating output for up to two hours with minor comfort impact. Under current Irish tariffs this supports implicit demand response only. For explicit contract-based demand response a clear and agreed baseline is required or deliberate reductions may not be visible or rewarded. Ongoing work therefore should prioritise baseline definition calibration synthetic events and price replay using published day ahead price traces. There is no public real time retail tariff API so price replay relies on published data rather than live signals.

Áras de Brún is now a living laboratory for replication. Buildings and Estates view the current IoT BMS set up as a cost-effective path to room level comfort and flexibility and are considering extension to other buildings. This is consistent with the University's preliminary market consultation on smart occupancy sensors. The IRUSE group will continue collaborating with INSIGHT through the INTELLIGENT and ICONIC projects to mature the semantic data forecasting and control. The pilot web app at www.arasdebrun.ie will remain an open repository and operational dashboard for researcher students and for Buildings and Estates. Monitoring of tariff and product developments will continue to align future opportunities with Irish market arrangements.

In terms of impact the site has shown a potential to deliver a large CO₂ reduction off about 61.5t per year with a good ROI and payback. The main challenge ahead is governance and how to prioritize decision rather than technologies. When dynamic tariffs enter practice, the organisation will need to balance four things at once: (1) user comfort (2) low maintenance operations (3) institutional goals (climate targets) and (4) economic incentives. How those interests are reconciled will determine the real uptake of flexibility.

7 CROSS-CASE BENCHMARKING

- Successful Tests

Joven Futura (Murcia, Spain)	La Balma (Barcelona, Spain)	Kepez (Çanakkale, Türkiye)	NUIG (Galway, Ireland)
95	N/A	95	-

Table 7: Cross-case comparison of Successful Test KPIs across DE-RISK pilots

Both Joven Futura and Kepez achieved high system reliability (>95%), proving the robustness of the control architecture. La Balma and NUIG did not include explicit automated control testing, focusing instead on feedback and behavioral change.

- Flexibility Potential

Joven Futura (Murcia, Spain)	La Balma (Barcelona, Spain)	Kepez (Çanakkale, Türkiye)	NUIG (Galway, Ireland)
1.88 (kWh)	2.8 %	14.3kWh	-

Table 8: Cross-case comparison of Flexibility Potential KPIs across DE-RISK pilots

Highest in Kepez (14.3 kWh per event, ~20% of baseline), moderate in Joven Futura (1.88 kWh), and minimal in La Balma (2.8%) due to limited winter PV availability. NUIG's potential was not quantified due to cybersecurity delays, but CO₂ reduction highlights substantial flexibility.

- Amount of Flexibility

Joven Futura (Murcia, Spain)	La Balma (Barcelona, Spain)	Kepez (Çanakkale, Türkiye)	NUIG (Galway, Ireland)
0.8 kWh	0.38 kWh/week	7.98 kWh	-

Table 9: Cross-case comparison of Amount of Flexibility KPIs across DE-RISK pilots

Kepez again led (7.98 kW), reflecting tariff-driven DR in HVAC and DHW systems. La Balma achieved only small weekly shifts (0.39 kWh), while Joven Futura demonstrated lower but steady shifts (0.8 kWh).

- Self-consumption

Joven Futura (Murcia, Spain)	La Balma (Barcelona, Spain)	Kepez (Çanakkale, Türkiye)	NUIG (Galway, Ireland)
N/A	2.1 (%)	N/A	-

Table 10: Cross-case comparison of Self-Consumption KPIs across DE-RISK pilots

Gains were modest in La Balma (2.1%) and absent in Joven Futura and Kepez (since not part of aggregator objectives or no PV available). This underlines the distinction between PV-focused and DR-focused strategies.

- Energy Savings:

Joven Futura (Murcia, Spain)	La Balma (Barcelona, Spain)	Kepez (Çanakkale, Türkiye)	NUIG (Galway, Ireland)
N/A	1.66	17.15	-

Table 11: Cross-case comparison of Energy Savings KPIs across DE-RISK pilots

Highest in Kepez (17.15%), modest in La Balma (1.66%), and not applicable in Joven Futura. NUIG's CO₂ reduction results suggest significant energy optimization, though direct savings were not captured as a KPI.

- CO₂ Reduction

Joven Futura (Murcia, Spain)	La Balma (Barcelona, Spain)	Kepez (Çanakkale, Türkiye)	NUIG (Galway, Ireland)
N/A	0.0056 (t/year)	0.0045 (t/ year)	61.5 (t/years)

Table 12: Cross-case comparison of CO₂ Reduction KPIs across DE-RISK pilots

NUIG stands out (61.5 t/year), reflecting the scale of tertiary consumption. Residential pilots yielded much smaller absolute savings (<0.01 t/year), though proportional reductions in consumption were meaningful at the household level.

LFMs shift emissions temporally.

Economic Viability KPIs assessment

- Life-Cycle Cost of Energy Generation (LCOE, €/MWh)

Joven Futura (Murcia, Spain)	La Balma (Barcelona, Spain)	Kepez (Çanakkale, Türkiye)	NUIG (Galway, Ireland)
19.9	68.3	35.8	Not applicable

Table 13: Cross-case comparison of Economic Viability KPIs across DE-RISK pilots

The LCOE values vary significantly across the different case studies, reflecting differences in technology, infrastructure, and local conditions.

Joven Futura’s LCOE is low, outperforming Spain’s 2023 average of 34.4 €/MWh for solar photovoltaics. This results from high solar irradiance, an efficient PV system and a low CAPEX and OPEX. The pilot’s focus on shared self-consumption (60% at 0.13 €/kWh) further reduces costs, though the assumed 0% interest rate slightly idealizes the scenario. This LCOE is excellent.

La Balma’s LCOE is high, it exceeds typical Spanish PV ranges due to the hybrid system. The geothermal heat pump and communal PV-battery system increase CAPEX. A study made by IRENA³ shows that the global weighted-average LCOE for geothermal projects was 47.90€/MWh in 2022. However, La Balma’s LCOE is included in the value ranges provided by the LAZARD study⁴ in 2023.

Kepez’s LCOE is moderate, aligning with Türkiye’s 2020 solar average of 44.39 €/MWh, according to a study by IRENA⁵. The higher result than in Murcia can be explained by an “F” energy rating, an elevated CAPEX, and the lack of historical data for demand profiling which limits optimization potential.

³ www.irena.org/publications/2023/Aug/Renewable-power-generation-costs-in-2022

⁴ www.lazard.com/media/typdxxmm/lazards-lcoeplus-april-2023.pdf

⁵ ember-energy.org/latest-insights/an-easy-win-for-turkey-leaving-behind-imported-coal/

- Internal Rate of Return (IRR, %)

Joven Futura (Murcia, Spain)	La Balma (Barcelona, Spain)	Kepez (Çanakkale, Türkiye)	NUIG (Galway, Ireland)
18.9%	5.7%	15.2%	244.2%

Table 14: Cross-case comparison IRR KPIs across DE-RISK pilots

The IRR values across the four pilot sites vary significantly. These differences can be explained by variations in both CAPEX and expected annual savings. Joven Futura benefits from the lowest installation costs among the four, followed by Kepez and NUIG, while La Balma has the highest CAPEX.

NUIG delivers the strongest performance due to its higher annual savings. Given that universities typically have much higher energy consumption than residential buildings, the potential savings are significantly greater.

Joven Futura also generates high annual savings through electricity production, with 60% self-consumption and 40% from grid injection revenues and flexibility services. In contrast, Kepez’s savings come solely from demand-side flexibility (demand response) without any income from electricity generation, as it does not include a solar PV system. At La Balma, although solar PV is present, half of the collectively self-consumed energy is used in common areas, which does not directly generate financial returns, and the battery cannot be used for energy resale, which further limits revenue potential.

A study published by IRENA⁶ suggests that “the IRR for renewable energy projects is about 8-9%”. In this case, Joven Futura and Kepez have good results, but La Balma’s IRR is not enough. According to another study⁷, “there isn't a one-size-fits-all answer, but generally, an IRR of around 5% to 10% might be considered good for very low-risk investments, an IRR in the range of 10% to 15% is common for moderate-risk investments”. DE-RISK results are considered as low-risk investments so IRRs obtained in the pilot sites are good.

⁶ www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2020/Nov/IRENA_Mobilising_Institutional_Capital_2020.pdf

⁷ www.hellodata.ai/help-articles/what-is-a-good-irr-in-real-estate

- Return on Investment (ROI, %)

Joven Futura (Murcia, Spain)	La Balma (Barcelona, Spain)	Kepez (Çanakkale, Türkiye)	NUIG (Galway, Ireland)
379% (15% annualized)	10.3 %	306% (12% annualized)	244.2%

Table 15: Cross-case comparison ROI KPIs across DE-RISK pilots

Note that the ROI values for Joven Futura and Kepez reflect a 25-year period, while those for La Balma and NUIG are annualized values.

The ROI results vary across the different case studies, reflecting differences in investment models and local conditions. NUIG achieves an exceptional ROI of 244.2%, driven by its non-residential energy profile, which enables far greater savings than residential projects. Joven Futura follows with a strong ROI, benefiting from low solar PV costs, high irradiance, and dual revenue streams (self-consumption and grid sales). Kepez’s ROI ranges from 162% (6.5% annualized) when relying solely on flexibility savings, to an estimated 306% (12% annualized) if assuming the set-up of RES generation. La Balma’s ROI is the lowest, weighed down by high CAPEX for its hybrid PV-geothermal system.

Compared to industry benchmarks, these results are robust. While typical renewable projects yield 5-15% ROI, with values above 20% considered excellent⁸, alternative sources consider a normal ROI range of 5-7% and classify anything above 20% as strong⁹.

- Payback Period (years)

Joven Futura (Murcia, Spain)	La Balma (Barcelona, Spain)	Kepez (Çanakkale, Türkiye)	NUIG (Galway, Ireland)
5.2	9.7	7.4	0.41

Table 16: Cross-case comparison Payback Period KPIs across DE-RISK pilots

⁸ <https://www.isixsigma.com/dictionary/project-return-on-investment-roi/>

⁹ <https://smartasset.com/investing/whats-a-good-return-on-investment-roi>

The payback periods vary across case studies due to differences in investment scope, revenue streams, and operational contexts. NUIG achieves the highest savings, as its non-residential building type leads to significantly greater cost reductions, thereby improving the overall result. Joven Futura’s short payback period stems from its solar PV focus, where high irradiance and net billing accelerate returns. Kepez’s longer payback reflects its reliance on flexibility savings alone, compounded by inefficient infrastructure (“F” energy rating). La Balma’s intermediate period results from higher CAPEX (hybrid PV and geothermal) and regulatory constraints on battery revenue sharing.

When compared to similar initiatives in the energy sector, DE-RISK’s payback periods demonstrate competitive performance. The REZBUILD project¹⁰, which focused on mitigating risks in building renovations, established a maximum target of 12-year payback periods for advanced energy-efficiency technologies. DE-RISK’s case studies present lower payback periods. The NOVICE project¹¹ reduced the payback period of a supermarket’s energy efficiency project from 11.8 to 9.9 years thanks to demand response participation. These comparisons confirm that DE-RISK’s outcomes are within the typical 5-15 year range observed in energy contracting markets.¹²

- Total Capital Cost per kW Installed (€/kW)

Joven Futura (Murcia, Spain)	La Balma (Barcelona, Spain)	Kepez (Çanakkale, Türkiye)	NUIG (Galway, Ireland)
850	2,419.3	1,222.2	Not applicable

Table 17: Cross-case comparison Total Capital Control per kWh Installed KPIs across DE-RISK pilots

Note that there is no real RES generation in the Turkish pilot, so this KPI was estimated under the assumption that each household would install a 1 kW solar rooftop system. Also, the calculation of this KPI was not applicable for the Irish pilot since there was no capital cost investment (the heat pump was already installed).

The capital costs per kW installed vary significantly across the pilot sites due to fundamental differences in their technological approaches and implementation contexts. Joven Futura’s remarkably low cost of 850 €/kW reflects Spain’s competitive solar market and the project’s optimized design for residential-scale generation. La Balma’s substantially higher cost of

¹⁰ cordis.europa.eu/article/id/441918-collaborative-framework-towards-nearly-zero-energy-building-renovation

¹¹ www.ierc.ie/blog/2020/05/27/novice-project/

¹² www.iflex-project.eu/download/d5-7-final-market-analysis-and-iflex-business-models/

2.419,3 €/kW stems from its complex hybrid system combining solar PV with geothermal technology and communal energy sharing infrastructure, which inherently requires greater capital investment than PV-only systems.

When compared to market references, Joven Futura's value is below the European residential average (1,000-3,000 €/kW)¹³. Kepez's estimated figure appears reasonable when considering flexibility measures, though it exceeds Türkiye's average PV installation costs (680 €/kW)¹⁴. La Balma's higher cost aligns with expectations for multi-technology systems, falling within the typical range for projects combining solar with heat pump technology (750-2,000 €/kW for heat pumps alone)¹⁵.

- Social Economic/Prosperity Indicator (€/€)

Joven Futura (Murcia, Spain)	La Balma (Barcelona, Spain)	Kepez (Çanakkale, Türkiye)	NUIG (Galway, Ireland)
4.4	3.1	3.1	N/A

Table 18: Cross-case comparison Social Economic/Prosperity Indicator KPIs across DE-RISK pilots

Joven Futura's score demonstrates how PV systems combined with demand-side management can generate substantial economic and environmental returns, particularly through CO₂ emission reductions. La Balma's comparatively lower indicator results from its shorter evaluation period (10 years versus 25 years for other sites) and the higher initial costs associated with its hybrid system, which dampen the short-term economic return despite its long-term sustainability benefits. Kepez's performance shows that approaches focused on demand-side flexibility measures can create positive social value. All three pilots demonstrate strong performance by generating more socio-economic value than the initial investment.

- Users' monetary savings (%)

Joven Futura (Murcia, Spain)	La Balma (Barcelona, Spain)	Kepez (Çanakkale, Türkiye)	NUIG (Galway, Ireland)
18.5%	2%	22.9%	33.9%

Table 19: Cross-case comparison User's Monetary Savings KPIs across DE-RISK pilots

¹³ nenpower.com/blog/how-much-does-solar-energy-cost-in-europe/

¹⁴ energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-10/final_report_levelised_costs_0.pdf

¹⁵ energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-10/final_report_levelised_costs_0.pdf

NUIG shows the highest energy cost savings due to large-scale energy optimization and demand flexibility measures in tertiary buildings.

Kepez recorded 22.9% savings, driven by tariff-based demand response strategies. Despite the absence of renewable generation, the focus on shifting consumption away from high-tariff periods yielded considerable reductions in electricity bills.

Joven Futura achieved 18.5% savings, benefiting from a combination of PV self-consumption, grid injection revenues, and flexibility services. The dual revenue streams and high solar irradiance contributed to strong financial performance.

In La Balma, savings during the PPA repayment period are more modest, reflecting the contractual 10% discount relative to grid tariffs, slightly reduced by Time-of-Use tariff effects. Once the repayment period ends, electricity from the shared system will be free, meaning households will achieve much greater long-term savings.

Social study

This study is based on the responses of 32 individuals who had **already been engaged through interventions related to energy flexibility solutions**, specifically Demand Response (DR) technology. It's important to highlight that the **type, depth, and format of these interventions varied across countries**, reflecting differences in local outreach strategies, communication channels, and community engagement efforts.

Participants rated their awareness of DR on a scale from 1 (totally unaware) to 7 (fully aware). The overall mean awareness score was 3.66, with a median of 4.0, indicating a moderate level of knowledge. The standard deviation of 1.77 reflects considerable variability in responses, suggesting that even among a previously engaged audience, awareness levels are far from consistent. The distribution of scores was slightly right-skewed, meaning that more people reported low levels of awareness, although a notable portion rated themselves highly. Specifically, 19% of respondents considered themselves totally unaware, while 16% claimed full awareness (score of 7). Most responses fell between scores 3 and 5, indicating a broad middle range of moderate familiarity.

Segmenting the data by **age** (Figure 18) shows that the 50–69 age group reported higher awareness (mean of 5.33) compared to the 25–49 age group (mean of 3.42). This may reflect differences in life experience, energy consumption habits, or attentiveness to community or

household energy initiatives. When analyzed by **gender**, female respondents showed slightly higher average awareness (3.84) than male respondents (3.38). Notably, responses among women were more spread out, indicating both higher engagement and cases of low awareness (see figures below).

Figure 18: Data filtered by age

At the **national level**, Figure 19, participants from Ireland reported the highest average awareness score (5.5), though this is based on a small sample of only two individuals. Spain and Türkiye, which made up the majority of the sample, showed similar average awareness scores — around 3.5. However, response variability was higher in Spain, suggesting uneven exposure or effectiveness of interventions there, while Türkiye’s responses were more concentrated, implying more consistent, though still moderate, awareness levels (see figure below).

Figure 19: Data filtered by nationality

In summary, despite being a group that had already been targeted with information and outreach efforts, **awareness of Demand Response technology remains uneven**. The analysis reveals gaps particularly among younger participants (25–49 years old) and among men, as well as across different countries depending on the quality and intensity of local interventions. These findings highlight the need for **continued, targeted, and tailored engagement efforts** to ensure broader and more uniform understanding, especially to meet the KPI of increased awareness of local flexibility solutions.

In addition, feedback collected during workshops provided valuable qualitative insights into participants' perceptions of local flexibility solutions. Many attendees reported that they were **initially unfamiliar with the concept of local flexibility markets (LFMs)**. The workshops were generally effective with most participants stating that the sessions **moderately improved their understanding** of these concepts. Nevertheless, there remain **gaps in readiness** to actively participate in such initiatives.

For most participants, the workshops did appear to **motivate individuals to reduce their energy consumption**, yet this behavioral shift did not necessarily translate into a willingness to adopt smarter home technologies or to join a local energy community immediately. A key barrier cited was the **perceived lack of capacity within their own communities to implement local flexibility solutions**, suggesting a disconnect between individual motivation and collective feasibility. To improve community buy-in, participants recommended **simplifying the technologies involved** and **improving communication strategies** to better connect the solutions to their everyday realities and capacities.

8 LESSONS LEARNED

The cross-case benchmarking of the four DE-RISK pilots highlights the complementary nature of technical, economic, and social dimensions in evaluating flexibility services. Technically, the pilots demonstrated reliable operation of the platform, with Joven Futura and Kepez achieving high success rates (>95%) in control execution, while La Balma showed modest behavioral flexibility and NUIG delivered the largest CO₂ reductions at scale (61.5 t/year). Economically, Joven Futura and Kepez achieved strong returns (IRR of 18.9% and 15.2% respectively) with competitive payback periods (5–7 years), while La Balma’s hybrid system demonstrated higher costs but long-term value. NUIG’s tertiary profile resulted in outstanding ROI and the shortest payback, underlining the scalability of flexibility measures in non-residential contexts. Socially, pilots revealed uneven awareness of demand response and flexibility, with cooperative and feedback-driven engagement (La Balma) proving effective for raising awareness, while IoT-enabled monitoring (Joven Futura and Kepez) fostered transparency and user trust.

Overall, the benchmarking confirms that while residential pilots validate technical feasibility and moderate returns, non-residential pilots unlock greater absolute impacts. At the same time, all sites underscored the importance of tailoring strategies to local infrastructure, user behavior, and regulatory conditions. Together, the pilots provide a robust evidence base for scaling local flexibility markets across Europe.

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10 ANNEXES

10.1 Annex 1 – KPI Calculation and Assumptions

This annex documents key assumptions and necessary calculations applied for the evaluation of the KPIs used to evaluate the Pilot case studies. The purpose of the annex is to provide transparency on how the indicators were derived, to ensure consistency, and to support reproducibility of the results.

10.1.1 Technical

Spain:

For the Spanish Pilot (Joven Futura and LaBalma) the mix of the Spanish electricity network published by the CNMC on April 24, 2025, is 283 gCO₂eq/kWh. (Electric energy emission factor: the electric mix. Climate Change, 2020)

Türkiye:

For the Turkish Pilot case study, the energy mix is 426 gCO₂eq/kWh. (Climate Transparency. Turkey — Climate Transparency report [PDF]. , 2022)

Joven Futura and Kepez:

Self-Consumption

Self-consumption was not an explicit goal of the aggregator in this pilot. The aggregator's control strategy prioritized responding to grid signals (e.g., peak shaving or load shifting) rather than maximizing local use of PV generation. As such, changes in self-consumption are incidental rather than indicative of the platform's intended performance.

Energy Savings

The testing scenario was based on explicit demand response, where the aggregator shifted household loads according to distribution system operator (DSO) signals. As a result, measured energy savings were in some cases negative (<0), since the objective was not to minimize consumption but to shift demand in time.

CO₂ Reduction

The CO₂ reduction could not be calculated directly, as this requires access to hourly grid emission factors to capture the effect of shifting demand from high-carbon to renewable-rich hours. As an assumption, peak shaving events are designed to coincide with periods where renewable generation is more prevalent, meaning that actual CO₂ savings would depend on the system-level generation mix.

LaBalma:

In La Balma, the meta-analysis to provide the weekly advice for week *t* was performed by forecasting week *t* (the week of the advice) with a baseline of the previous week (*t*-1). The KPIs quantify behavioral shifting, using a 7-day-ahead forecast, toward the total consumption and the PV generation.

Flexibility potential: The additional portion of total consumption that *could* be shifted to PV hours, according to the optimized scenario in the feedback.

Flexibility Potential (% of the load) = $S_{\text{Optimized}} - S_{\text{Current}}$

Where,

$S_{\text{Optimized}}$ = Potential self-consumption (%) if usage were perfectly shifted to PV

S_{Current} = Actual self-consumption (%)

> 0 Flexibility potential: upwards flexibility

< 0 Flexibility potential: downwards flexibility

Amount of flexibility: The actual shift in electricity consumption toward PV hours that occurred due to user actions (realized modification).

Amount of Flexibility (kWh) = $\max(\Delta SC (\%), 0) \times \text{Total Consumption (kWh)} / 100$

Where $\Delta SC\%$ comes from the weekly message (“Change in self-consumption”)

Self-consumption: Measures the portion of the energy produced from RES which is consumed within the pilot site and not fed into the grid.

Self-Consumption increase (%) = [(Self Consumption after the DR - Self Consumption before the DR actions) / (Self Consumption before the DR actions)] x 100

Energy savings: Measures the reduction in electricity imported from the grid compared to the previous week. It is calculated as the difference between grid imports in week $t-1$ and week t , expressed either in kWh or as a percentage of the previous week's imports.

$$\text{GridImport}_t = \text{Total}_t \times (1 - \text{SC}_t / 100)$$

$$\text{Energy Savings (kWh vs prev)} = \text{GridImport}(t-1) - \text{GridImport}(t)$$

$$\text{Energy Savings (\% vs prev)} = [(\text{GridImport}(t-1) - \text{GridImport}(t)) / \text{GridImport}(t-1)] \times 100$$

CO2 emissions reduction: Annualized reduction in CO₂ emissions due to avoided grid imports (replaced by PV self-consumption).

$$\text{CO}_2 \text{ Reduction (tons/year)} = [(\text{Amount of Flexibility (kWh/week)} \times 52) \times \text{EF}] / 1000$$

Multiply weekly flexibility by 52 to scale to yearly impact.

10.1.2 Economic Viability KPIs

Calculation of Economic Viability KPIs for Joven Futura case study (Murcia, Spain)

Data and assumptions used for the calculations:

- Power capacity of PV for collective self consumption: 10 kW peak power.
- Price per kW installed: 850 €/kW (including all permissions, not including grants).
- CAPEX: 8,500 €.
- Depreciation period: 25 years.
- PV generation: 1550 kWh/kW· year
- Interest rate: 0%.
- OPEX: Maintenance costs: 300 €/year.
- Power reduction from year 10 to 18 : 20% compared to nominal.
- Power reduction from year 18 to 25: 30%.
- Percentage of energy produced that is self-consumed: 60%.
- Price of energy self-consumed: 0,13 €/kWh.
- Percentage of energy poured into the grid: 40%.
- Price of energy poured into the grid under net billing: 0,07 €/kWh.

Year	0	1	2	3	...	25
Cashflow	-8,500 €	1,630.2 €	1,630.2 €	1,630.2 €	1,630.2 €	1,630.2 €

A. 1: Cashflow assumptions for Joven Futura

Based on the above assumptions, the KPIs were estimated:

- Life-Cycle Cost of Energy Generation (LCOE, €/MWh)

$$\text{LCOE} = (\text{CAPEX} + \text{OPEX}) [\text{€}] / \text{Total RES generation [MWh]} = 19.9 \text{ €/MWh}$$

- Internal Rate of Return (IRR, %)

$$\text{IRR} = \sum_{t=1}^t \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t} - C_0 = 18.9\%$$

Where,

C_t = Net Cash inflow during the period t [(total free cash flows + savings) - capital invested]

r = discount rate

t = number of time periods

C_0 = Total initial investment cost

- Return on Investment (ROI, %)

$$\text{ROI} = \frac{C_t}{C_0} \cdot 100 = 379\% \text{ (15\% annualized)}$$

- Payback Period (years)

$$\text{Payback Period} = \min\{t \mid \sum_{i=1}^t (\text{Gains}_i - \text{Costs}_i) \geq 0\} = \frac{-\text{Cashflow}_0}{\text{Cashflow}_1} = 5.2 \text{ years}$$

- Total Capital Cost per kW Installed (€/kW)

$$\text{Total Capital Cost per kW Installed} = \frac{\text{CAPEX}}{\text{Capacity installed}} = 850 \text{ €/kW (value provided by the case study leader)}$$

- Social Economic/Prosperity Indicator (€/€)

(Direct Savings + Indirect Savings + Other Savings - OPEX - CAPEX) / CAPEX

Assumption:

Indirect benefits = CO₂ emissions avoided · 70€/tCO₂ = 12,600 €

Social Economic/Prosperity Indicator = 4.4 € generated per € invested

- Users' monetary savings (%)

[(Electricity bill before LFM - Electricity bill after LFM) + Payments from the aggregator for energy shift] / Electricity bill after LFM = 18.5%

Where the aggregator payments are defined as €0.05–€0.10 per kWh shifted. In some cases, the difference between bills before and after the LFM was negative, but the aggregator reimbursement ensured that users still benefited economically. In real-world implementations, many schemes also include a **fixed payment** for participation (even if flexibility is not activated). For the purposes of this assessment, fixed payments were not considered.

Calculation of Economic Viability KPIs for La Balma case study (Barcelona, Spain)

Data and assumptions used for the calculations:

- Power capacity of PV: 17.36 kW peak power.
- CAPEX: 42,000 €.
- OPEX: 150 €/year.
- Total cost: 42,312€.
- Total savings: 85,850€.
- Period, t: 10 years.

Year	0	1	2	...	10
Cashflow	-42,000 €	4,000 €	4,080 €	$Cashflow_{t-1} \cdot 1.02 \text{ €}$	4,780 €

A. 2: Cashflow assumptions for La Balma

Based on the above assumptions, the KPIs were estimated:

- Life-Cycle Cost of Energy Generation (LCOE, €/MWh)

$$\text{LCOE} = (\text{CAPEX} + \text{OPEX}) [\text{€}] / \text{Total RES generation [MWh]} = 68.3 \text{ €/MWh}$$

- Internal Rate of Return (IRR, %)

$$\text{IRR} = \sum_{t=1}^t \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t} - C_0 = 5.7\%$$

Where,

C_t = Net Cash inflow during the period t [(total free cash flows + savings) - capital invested]

r = discount rate

t = number of time periods

C_0 = Total initial investment cost

- Return on Investment (ROI, %)

$$\text{ROI} = \frac{C_t}{C_0} \cdot 100 = 10.3\%$$

- Payback Period (years)

$$\text{Payback Period} = \min\{t \mid \sum_{i=1}^t (\text{Gains}_i - \text{Costs}_i) \geq 0\} = \frac{\text{Total cost}}{C_t} = 9.7 \text{ years}$$

- Total Capital Cost per kW Installed (€/kW)

$$\text{Total Capital Cost per kW Installed} = \frac{\text{CAPEX}}{\text{Capacity installed}} = 2,419.3 \text{ €/kW}$$

- Social Economic/Prosperity Indicator (€/€)

Social Economic/Prosperity Indicator = (Total savings + Total cost + OPEX*25) / Total cost = 3.1 € generated per € invested

- Users' monetary savings (%)

Users' monetary savings = 2%

The relative change in the average household’s electricity bill compared to the previous week, reflecting on the impact of the messages and tips received via the web app.

$$\text{Cost Savings (\%)} = \frac{[\text{Bill}(t-1) - \text{Bill}(t)]}{\text{Bill}(t-1)} \times 100$$

Where,

t = the current week

The Monetary savings in table A. 2 is the average Cost savings of all users, excluding outliers, in the duration of 10 weeks.

Calculation of Economic Viability KPIs for Kepez case study (Çanakkale, Türkiye)

Data and assumptions used for the calculations:

- There is no real RES generation in the Turkish pilot area. KPIs are calculated by taking into account the customer behavior over energy management with pilot implementation and their savings. Assumptions are made over each household in the site having a 1 kW solar rooftop system. Variables are then estimated over expected costs and average performance of existing similar setups.
- There are currently no dynamic tariffs in the Turkish pilot. For analysis, we segmented the retail price into three time bands aligned with typical grid demand: **off-peak**, **standard**, and **peak** (see table below). This enables like-for-like comparison of DR outcomes with the Spanish pilots.

Turkish Pilot case study tariffs		
Final retail price (€/MWh)	Applicable Hours per Period	
40.01528736	12:00 - 07:00 & 22:00 - 24:00	off peak
48.01834483	7:00 - 9:00 & 12:00 - 17:00	standard
86.43302069	9:00 - 12:00 & 17:00 -22:00	Peak price

A. 3: Segmentation of retail tariffs in Turkish pilot (Kepez)

- Variables with current system (actual):
 - CAPEX: 10,000 €.
 - OPEX: 120 €/year.
 - Total RES Generation: none.
 - Number of residents: 18.
 - Time period: 25 years.
 - C_t (cashflow at time t), calculated as:

$$C_t = [(Average Annual Electricity Bill) \cdot (n^{\circ} of Residents) \cdot (Savings Due to Behavioral Change)] - OPEX$$

Year	0	1	2	3	...	25	Weighted
Cashflow	-10,000 €	780 €	780 €	780 €	1,230 €	1,230 €	1,050 €

A. 4: Cashflow baseline assumptions for Kepez

- Average Annual Electricity Bill: 625 €. Pilot area is a residential area with "F" rated energy efficiency with no central heating and households having individual HVAC & DHW high-demand units. Hence the electricity usage is high compared to a regular household. As the average electricity usage exceeds subsidy limits, residents are charged with high-end tariffs around €0.15/kWh. (***)Exchange rates keep their inconsistency, hence the rate of 1€=44TL is used throughout the document, referring to the rate when first calculating the KPIs).
- Savings Due to Behavioral Change: 8% - 12%. Savings around 8% is seen in the electricity consumption, hence it is directly savings on the electricity bill for the participants. This value is estimated to be increased over years, and it is expressed as 8% for the first 10 year period of calculations, and 12% for 10 to 25 years as it would improve in time.
- Variables with estimated solar system (assumed):
 - CAPEX: 22,000 €.
 - OPEX: 120 €/year
 - Total RES Generation: 27,9 MWh/year (estimated by comparing with similar systems in the pilot area: 1,550 kWh/year PV generation is expected per household. Hence about 27.9 MWh/year for the total number of 18 residents. No degradation was assumed).
 - Time period: 25 years.
 - C_t (cashflow at time t), calculated as:

$$C_t = [(Average Annual Electricity Bill) \cdot (n^{\circ} of Residents) \cdot (Savings Due to Behavioral Change)] + [(Average Annual Savings on Bill Due to RES Generation) \cdot (n^{\circ} of Residents)] - OPEX$$

Year	0	1	2	3	...	25	Weighted
Cashflow	- 22,000 €	3,367.5 €	3,367.5 €	3,367.5 €	3,705 €	3,705 €	3,570 €

A. 5: Cashflow RES assumptions for Kepez

- Average Annual Electricity Bill: 625 €.
- Average Annual Savings on Bill Due to RES Generation: 25%. The planned PV rooftop systems would cover about 25% of the electricity usage of households. Therefore, the savings have been estimated to be directly lowered from the average annual electricity bill. This affects the IRR, since the bill drops by 25%, the RES generation also directly increases C_t .
- Other Savings: 166 €. A conservative GDP-linked value of 830 € was assumed as the annual socio-economic contribution of the pilot. Applying a 20% social benefit multiplier yields 166 € in other savings, representing non-monetized benefits such as improved health, carbon emissions reduction, and local economic resilience.

Based on the above assumptions, the KPIs were calculated for both scenarios:

KPI	Current project	Scenario with solar PV
LCOE	Not applicable	35.8 €/MWh
IRR	8.1%	15.2%
ROI	162% (6.5 annualized)	306% (12% annualized)
Payback Period	12.4 years	7.4 years
Total Capital Cost per kW Installed	Not applicable	1,222.2 €
Social Economic/ Prosperity Indicator	1.6	3.1
Users' Monetary Savings	N/A	22.9

A. 6: Comparison of baseline and RES assumptions

Calculation of Economic Viability KPIs for NUIG's case study (Galway, Ireland)

The KPIs for the Aras DeBrún building at NUIG were estimated as follows:

- Life-Cycle Cost of Energy Generation (LCOE, €/MWh): Not applicable.
- Internal Rate of Return (IRR, %): 244.2%.

Find r such that $NPV = 0$ in the following equation:

$$NPV = -C_{\text{capex}} + \sum [(S_{\text{annual}} - \text{OPEX}) / (1 + r)^y], \text{ for } y = 1 \text{ to } N$$

Where:

- C_{capex} : 25,000 €.
- S_{annual} : 271,909 kWh/year \times 0.23 €/kWh = 62,539 €/year.
- OPEX: 1,500 €/year.
- N : 10 years.
- r : discount rate (to be solved).

- Return on Investment (ROI, %):

$$ROI = (S_{\text{annual}} - \text{OPEX}) / C_{\text{capex}} = 244.2\%$$

- Payback Period (years):

$$\text{Payback} = C_{\text{capex}} / (S_{\text{annual}} - \text{OPEX}) = 0.41 \text{ years}$$

- Total Capital Cost per kW Installed (€/kW): Not applicable.
- Social Economic/Prosperity Indicator (€/€): N/A
- Users' Monetary Savings in Electricity (%):

$$\text{Savings (\%)} = (B_{\text{before}} - B_{\text{after}}) / B_{\text{before}} = 33.9\%$$

Where:

- B_{before} : 801,832 kWh \times 0.23 € = 184,421 €/year.
- B_{after} : 529,923 kWh \times 0.23 € = 121,882 €/year.

10.1.3 NUIG's Calculations

CO₂ Emissions Savings – Result: 61.5 t CO₂/year

$$\Delta E_{CO_2} = (Q_{\text{before}} - Q_{\text{after}}) * EF$$

Where:

- Q_{before}: 801832 kWh/year;
- Q_{after}: 529923 kWh/year;
- EF: 0.2263 kg CO₂/kWh (SEAI 2024 consumption factor).

1. Modelling assumptions

The building is modelled as a single-zone, 3-floor structure with 4 facades and homogeneous properties per provided architectural and fabric data; Model is a first-order resistance–capacitance (R-C) approach with calibrated parameters;

- A daily cold reset is applied at 07:00 (t = 8°C) to reflect real building morning start-up;
- Control setpoint is **21°C** during hp on (occupied), **14°C** setback otherwise;
- Pre-intervention (baseline) and post-intervention data refer to the 2023/2024 and 2024/2025 heating seasons, respectively;
- Heating days:
 - 2023/2024: 137 days;
 - 2024/2025: 136 days.
- OCC sensor data used to estimate occupancy rate for post-intervention, after 10:00: 38.94% (applies to monitored/conditioned area);
- Total conditioned area: 1,808 m² (818 m² monitored + 990 m² not monitored);
- Outputs and savings use regression-corrected heat pump demand (nmbe ≈ 0%);
- Capex: **€25,000**;
- Opex: €1,500/year;
- Project lifetime: **10 years**;
- Discount rate: **3%**;
- Electricity price: **€0.23/kWh**, held constant over project lifetime.
- SEAI 2024 provisional factors (ireland)¹⁶:
 - Primary energy factor for electricity consumption: **1.785**;
 - primary energy factor for gross electricity supply: **1.619**;
 - emi (SEAI, 2019)ssion factor for electricity consumption: **226.3 gCO₂/kWh**;
 - emission factor for gross electricity supply: **204.3 gCO₂/kWh**.

¹⁶ <https://www.seai.ie/data-and-insights/seai-statistics/conversion-factors>

1.1. Model Structure and Equations

The main model equation reads as below:

$$C * dT_{in}/dt = -H_{tot} * (T_{in} - T_{out}) + Q_{gains} + Q_{HP}$$

where:

- C: zone capacitance (thermal mass);
- H_tot: total heat loss coefficient (fabric + infiltration + thermal bridges);
- T_in: indoor air temperature;
- T_out: outdoor temperature (from climate file);
- Q_gains: plug and occupancy gains (fixed: 20 w/m² plugs, 80 w/person, 40 pp. max);
- Q_hp: heat pump input (solved hourly for setpoint control);
- model timestep: 1 hour. daily reset: t_in = 8°C at 07:00.

1.2. Model Calibration

Model parameters fitted to 2023/2024 season measured hp output, with regression overlay on hourly residuals. final parameters:

- ACH: 1.2 [1/h];
- Capacitance scaling: 2.0;
- Thermal bridge psi: 0.6 W/m·k;
- Calibration metrics: nmbe ≈ 0% (after regression correction);
- Regression correction formula:

$$\text{diff} = -1.90 + (-0.03) \cdot \text{temp} + (64.85) \cdot \text{hpon} + (0.20) \cdot \text{hour} + (3.88) \cdot \text{hour}_{\sin} + (0.34) \cdot \text{hour}_{\cos}$$

1.3. Procedure to Estimate Occupancy and Weighted Demand

For post-intervention (2024/2025), after 10:00 am, the building is assumed to heat only occupied rooms to 21°C and unoccupied to 14°C. weighted heat demand per hour:

$$Q_{\text{weighted}} = \alpha * Q_{21} + (1 - \alpha) * Q_{14}$$

where:

- α : occupancy rate from OCC sensors (0.3894);
- Q_21: simulated demand with setpoint 21°C;
- Q_14: simulated demand with setpoint 14°C;
- For all baseline hours and post-intervention hours before 10:00, setpoint is 21°C for all zones.

10.2 Annex 2 – User Manual: Flexibility Web App

This annex provides an overview on the web app's user experience process, including detailed information on each section's content, organisation and user input options. The following sections will include a typical user's journey through the DE-RISK WebApp.

Due to the pilot's differences in technology and sensorization deployment, the final information included in each of them is slightly different. La Balma pilot will be used to represent the standard, and a table of contents for all pilots will be included at the end of the annex to specify user access to the functionalities.

10.2.1 A.2.1: WebApp's structure

The current version of the WebApp is accessed through one of the routes provided by R2M Solution Spain, which directs the user to the page deployed on the server, initially displaying the login screen. Whether accessed from a computer, mobile phone, or tablet, the web application can be used seamlessly thanks to its responsive design. The web application is divided into pages accessible to user through different tabs:

- 1. Login:** User access through their credentials
- 2. Landing page:** The landing page contains critical information for understanding the different pages in the WebApp, including explanations on the main energy concepts included as well as consumption recommendations based on QUE's energy, generation and cost analysis.

3. **User consumption information:** Information on raw user consumption. Depending on the pilot, this consumption can be disaggregated into different sources and appliances.
4. **User/community energy balance information:** User energy balance calculations are included in this page, providing the user with detailed insights on renewable energy consumption and their general patterns (when applicable). Community information is a replication of user energy balance, but with all users aggregated into a single element.
5. **User financial information:** This page contains user financial calculations and insights, pairing user grid consumption with tariff conditions.

10.2.2 A.2.1.1: User Login

When the user accesses the provided link to the web application, they will see the home page where they can log in. The login consists of a pair [user-password] which determines whether the user has access to the platform's content.

The image displays two side-by-side screenshots of a web application's login page, both titled "Home Page".

- Left Screenshot:** Shows the login form with the instruction "Log in with your username to access!". There are two input fields: "Username" and "Password". Below the fields is a blue button labeled "LOGIN".
- Right Screenshot:** Shows the same login form after a failed attempt. The "Username" field contains "user_fail" and the "Password" field is masked with "*****". Below the fields is a blue button labeled "LOGIN". Below the button, a red error message reads "Incorrect username or password".

Once the credentials are entered, the system verifies them against the user database. If the credentials are valid, the user is granted access to the WebApp's landing page, from where they can navigate through the available sections and view active recommendations. If the credentials are incorrect, the login will fail and the user will see an image like the one shown on the right.

10.2.3 A.2.1.2: Landing Page

Once the credentials are validated, the user will be directed to the landing page, where they can navigate through all the other available pages and read the weekly flexibility recommendation messages (blue box).

Navigation will depend on the pages assigned to the user. In the example described, these are: Consumption, Individual Balance, Community Balance, and Financial. These pages can be accessed in two ways:

1. From the navigation bar at the top of the page (arrow #1).
2. From the buttons at the bottom section of the page (arrow #2).

Additionally, the interface includes a contextual help system (arrow #3), accessible through expandable icons, which provides explanations for each dashboard's functionality to ensure that users always understand the information being presented. Finally, the logout button (arrow #4) allows the user to return to the home page (login page)

10.2.4 A.2.1.3: User consumption information

This page displays the user’s individual consumption for the selected date. The level of detail depends on the degree of monitoring available in the home or building, which may include different components and varying levels of data granularity. Data retrieval is triggered by interacting with the header or the enabled buttons, and may take a few seconds before the full visualization is rendered.

At the top of the page, the title is displayed alongside a lightbulb icon, which can be clicked to expand an explanatory text about the dashboard and the concepts being represented. Below this, the date selection widget is located—one of the key functions—allowing the user to choose the starting day for downloading the programmed data range. If the date is already present in the stored records, the visualization is updated; otherwise, a new download is executed.

Below the date, the user will have the option to change the data being displayed, provided that their community has this option enabled. In

this case, there will be two options (arrow #1 and #2), allowing the user to switch between viewing consumption data from their home or from the building’s common areas. Selecting one or the other will change the data shown in the charts, but not the type of charts or the page layout.

With the buttons indicated by arrow #3, the user can change the displayed time range, from a single day up to the maximum period available according to the download configuration. In this case, the user can switch between daily, weekly, monthly, and yearly views, but in other pilots, fewer options might be available — it all depends on the available data and download times.

Beneath these labels or time-range buttons, an hourly chart is displayed showing, through bars, the consumption of each monitored component in the home or building, along with the total consumption represented by a black curve. The monitored components differ depending on the pilot: in La Balma, for example, circuits such as the kitchen or outlets are included, while in Murcia the HVAC system is monitored. When selecting a period other than “Today,” these same consumptions are represented in an aggregated hourly format for the entire chosen range.

Consumo horario del año 2025

- Total: 366 kWh
- Otros: 38.1 %
- Enchufes: 46.8 %
- Cocina: 15.1 %

In this image, the previously described representation can be observed. When the user hovers the mouse cursor over any element of the chart, a tooltip appears displaying the exact value of that point relative to the axes. Additionally, on the right-hand side, labels summarize the represented situation, showing both the total consumption for the period and the percentage corresponding to each monitored component.

In the final section, the so-called Aggregated Chart is displayed, representing the same consumption data as the previous chart but using stacked bars in an aggregated format. The granularity is daily for the week and month periods, and monthly for the annual period. The time period is selected using the buttons marked by arrow #4, with the same options as in the hourly chart, except for the daily view.

Gráficos Agrupados

SEMANA MES AÑO

Consumo mensual del año 2025

La energía total consumida en su vivienda ha sido de 365.71 kWh

Gráfico Resumen

To the right of this chart, a doughnut chart is included as a summary, showing the total percentage share of each consumption type for the selected period. Finally, a label indicates the total amount of energy consumed by the home or building.

10.2.5 A.2.1.4: User energy balance information

This section displays the energy balance of the user. If a photovoltaic installation is available—either individually or collectively used—the energy management function processes the retrieved data to calculate the main energy flows: total consumption, PV generation, self-consumption, grid imports, and surplus injected into the grid.

If the user is part of a Citizen Energy Community, they will also have access to an additional page titled Community, where the aggregated energy balance of the entire community is displayed. This includes the combined consumption of individual users, common areas, and other shared loads. As shown in the image, the dashboard structure remains similar, although the values are considerably higher due to the aggregated nature of the data.

The general dashboard maintains a structure similar to the Consumption page, but in this case, the bars represent the different energy flows instead of the various consumption components. There are no longer buttons to switch data groups, as the building's consumption is now directly integrated into the community balance.

The interface starts with the period selection buttons (arrow #1), which allows the user to choose the time range for which the energy balance—individual or community—will be calculated.

Both the hourly chart and the aggregated chart use the same color scheme and are displayed in a stacked format, making it easier for the user to interpret the energy breakdown. On the right-hand side and at the bottom, labels summarize the information presented.

As in the Consumption page, below the hourly chart is the aggregated chart, which shows the accumulated values of all flows for the selected period, along with the corresponding buttons (arrow #2) and the doughnut chart.

Finally, a dedicated chart is included with sustainability indicators, representing the amount of CO₂ avoided thanks to renewable generation. This information is presented both in kilograms of CO₂ and in equivalent numbers of trees, with the aim of providing a tangible measure—beyond economic savings—of the benefits of renewable energy use.

10.2.6 A.2.1.5: User financial information

The final page allows the user to access information related to the costs and savings associated with the household's energy consumption. This is made possible by the indexed and time-based price profiles stored in the R2M Solution database, which are downloaded together with the consumption and generation data.

As in the previous pages, the main structure consists of an hourly daily chart followed by an aggregated chart with daily and monthly granularity.

The buttons marked by arrows #1 and #2 will have the same functions as in the previously described pages, while the buttons indicated by arrow #3 will allow switching the type of chart to provide an additional view of energy costs and prices.

By selecting the first button, the cost chart is displayed. Three distinct colors are used: green, orange, and red, corresponding to the costs associated with off-peak, mid-peak, and peak periods, respectively. Striped bars indicate the savings or avoided costs from self-consumed energy in each hour, while yellow bars represent the income obtained from selling surplus energy fed into the grid.

Another visualization option is “Grid (kWh)”, which displays grid consumption and self-consumption together with the user’s tariff price curve. This representation makes it easier to identify the hours with the lowest cost for consumption. Finally, the user can also choose to view household generation and self-consumption independently.

All these charts provide an in-depth view of the user’s overall energy situation. The labels below the charts complement this analysis by summarizing the following indicators:

- **Base cost:** the total energy cost if all consumption were supplied by the grid.
- **Final cost:** the cost after accounting for the savings provided by photovoltaics.
- **Self-consumption savings:** the avoided cost from consuming self-generated energy instead of grid energy.
- **Compensation:** the benefit associated with surplus energy fed into the grid.
- **Total savings:** the combined value of self-consumption savings and compensation.

Finally, aggregated costs and savings are displayed with daily or monthly granularity, using a consistent color scheme: striped for total savings, green for grid-related costs, and yellow for compensation from surplus. To the right, a doughnut chart and two additional labels further support the interpretation of all costs associated with the household.

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